

Research article

Additional records of family Dolichopodidae (Diptera: Empidoidea) for the fauna of the Balkan Mountains, Bulgaria

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Abstract: The paper gives information about 21 dolichopodid species distributed in the Balkan Mountains, Bulgaria. Four of them are newly recorded for the studied region, as for *Chrysotus hubenovi* described soon, it is the second locality for Bulgaria and for the Palaearctic realm in general. For *Dolichopus linearis* known also with one locality from Bulgaria this research provides two new ones.

Keywords: Balkan Mountains, *Chrysotus hubenovi*, Dolichopodidae, fauna, new records

Introduction

Family Dolichopodidae encompasses small to medium sized predatory flies (from 1 to 10 mm). The family is one of the most species-rich of Diptera Brachycera in the world, with about 8000 species known so far. For the fauna of Bulgaria are known 211 dolichopodids and for the Balkan Mountains the number is 72 species up to now (Kechev & Koychev, 2021).

The main purpose of this work is to provide new data for the distribution of the family Dolichopodidae for the Balkan Mountains.

Material and methods

The material for the present work was collected in the studied area by the authors from eight localities with a sweeping net plus in one locality with Malaise trap by D. Ganeva and T. Ljubomirov (Fig. 1). After collecting, the adults have been stored in vials containing 75% ethanol. The species have been sorted in the laboratory, using a stereo microscope Carl Zeiss. For the determination of dolichopodids identification guides

by Parent (1938), Negrobov & Stackelberg (1969), d'Assis Fonseca (1978) and Grichanov (2007) have been used. The material presented in this paper is kept in Mihail Kechev's collection at the Department of Forest Entomology, Phytopathology and Game Fauna, Forest Research Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, Bulgaria.

Collecting sites

- Site 1 Tserovo Village, near Svoge, Iskar River (Fig. 2), 21.ix.2022, 43.0086°N 23.3524°E, 432 m a.s.l., sweeping net, M. Kechev & B. Koychev
- Site 2 Cherepish monastery, Iskar River, 24.vii.2022, 43.0952°N 23.6136°E, 261 m a.s.l., sweeping net, B. Koychev
- Site 3 Lyutibrod Village, Iskar River, 24.vii.2022, 43.1089°N 23.6272°E, 234 m a.s.l., sweeping net, B. Koychev
- Site 4 Rebarkovo Village, Iskar River, 43.1132°N 23.6762°E, 223 m a.s.l., sweeping net, B. Koychev
4a – 5.vi.2022
4b – 24.vii.2022

Fig. 1. Map of the Balkan Mountains with localities of collecting.

Site 5 Kreta Village, Vratsa District, Iskar River, 43.1208°N 23.7013°E (Fig. 3), 220 m, sweeping net, B. Koychev

5a – 19.vi.2022

5b – 8.vii.2022

5c – 12.viii.2022

5d – 28.viii.2022

Site 6 Mezdra, Iskar River, 19.vi.2022, 43.1338°N 23.7044°E, 210 m a.s.l., sweeping net, B. Koychev

Site 7 near Kalofer Monastery, 20.vii–1.viii.2010, 42.641355°N 24.950285° E, 530 m a.s.l., Malaise trap, D. Ganeva & T. Ljubomirov

Site 8 Planinitsa Village, 27.vii.2022, 42.891613°N 27.172142°E (Fig. 4), 242 m a.s.l., sweeping net, M. Kechev.

Faunistic results

Diaphorinae

Asyndetus latifrons (Loew, 1857) – Material examined: site 3: 1 ♂.

Chrysotus angulicornis Kowarz, 1874 – Material examined: site 3: 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀.

Fig. 2. Iskar River near Tserovo Village.

Fig. 3. Iskar River near Kreta Village.

Fig. 4. A small streamlet near fountain in Planinitza Village.

Fig. 5. *Chrysotus hubenovi* Kechev, Naglis, Negrobov, 2022, female: A – habitus, B – head.

Chrysotus cilipes Meigen, 1824 – Material examined: site 4b: 2 ♂♂; site 5a: 3 ♂♂.

Chrysotus femoratus Zetterstedt, 1843 – Material examined: site 4b: 4 ♂♂.

Chrysotus hubenovi Kechev, Naglis, Negrobov, 2022 (Fig. 5) – Material examined: site 7: 1 ♀. First record for the Balkan Mountains.

Chrysotus laesus (Wiedemann, 1817) – Material examined: site 6: 1 ♂.

Fig. 6. *Rhabdium micans* (Meigen, 1824), habitus.

Dolichopodinae

Dolichopus linearis Meigen, 1824 – Material examined: site 4a: 1 ♂; site 5a: 1 ♂. First record for the Balkan Mountains.

Dolichopus pennatus Meigen, 1824 – Material examined: site 5b: 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀.

Gymnopternus aerosus (Fallén, 1823) – Material examined: site 1: 1 ♂.

Hercostomus plagiatus (Loew, 1857) – Material examined: site 5a: 2 ♀♀. First record for the Balkan Mountains.

Tachytrechus notatus (Stannius, 1831) – Material examined: site 5d: 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀. First record for the Balkan Mountains.

Medeteranae

Medetera micacea Loew, 1857 – Material examined: site 8: 2 ♂♂.

Thrypticus bellus Loew, 1869 – Material examined: site 5d: 1 ♂.

Chrysotimus molliculus (Fallén, 1823) – Material examined: site 2: 26 ♂♂, 9 ♀♀; site 3: 2 ♂♂.

Rhaphiinae

Rhabdium appendiculatum Zetterstedt, 1849 – Material examined: site 5c: 1 ♂.

Rhabdium caliginosum Meigen, 1824 – Material examined: site 5b: 1 ♂; 5c: 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀.

Rhabdium micans (Meigen, 1824) (Fig. 6) – Material examined: site 2: 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀.

Sympycninae

Sympycnus pulicarius (Fallén, 1823) – Material examined: site 5d: 2 ♂♂.

Sympycnus simplicipes Becker, 1908 – Material examined: site 5d: 1 ♂.

Syntormon pallipes (Fabricius, 1794) – Material examined: site 5b: 2 ♂♂; site 8: 1 ♂.

Teuchophorus monacanthus Loew, 1859 – Material examined: site 5d: 1 ♂.

Discussion

Four dolichopodid species are recorded for the first time for the Balkan Mountains in the territory of Bulgaria. For the species *Chrysotus hubenovi*, described from the West Rhodope Mountains from 1100 m altitude (Kechev et al., 2022), this work gives the second locality from Kaloferska Planina Mt at an altitude of 530 m. The species *Dolichopus linearis* until now was known in Bulgaria with only one locality – one male specimen from the town of Chirpan (Kechev, 2011) – and here we reported two new ones.

Hercostomus plagiatus was known with two localities in Bulgaria, Basha Place, near Chirpan and Sarnena Sredna Gora Mt, Chehlaré Village. This species inhabits riverbeds and small ponds in Bulgaria (Kechev & Ivanova, 2015; Kechev, 2016).

Tachytrechus notatus is widespread in Bulgaria and is known from Pancharevo (Nedelkov, 1912), Varna, on the sea rocks (Beschovski, 1964), Gorno Belevó Village, along the banks of Omurovska River (Kechev et al. 2014).

Rhabdium micans distributed throughout all Europe and for the Balkan Mts was published from the Serbian part of the mountain (Grichanov, 2016). For Bulgaria it was known from two localities so far. The first one is Sofia (Nedelkov, 1912) and the second locality Rebarokovo Village in the Balkan Mts (Kechev & Koychev, 2021), situated close to the one pointed out in this study. This species does not appear to be as widespread as the other two species of the genus *Rhabdium* mentioned above – *Rh. appendiculatum* and *Rh. caliginosum*, which are known from many localities in the country and from different habitats.

With this research the total number of the dolichopodid species for the Balkan Mountains is increasing to 76.

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